

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE FAMILY IN CHILDHOOD RAISING

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Annotation: *In this article, you will learn about the role of preschool education, family and society in the upbringing of children.*

Keys words: *child rearing, family rearing, community impact, small state, rearing departments*

Education is a social phenomenon. It has existed since the dawn of human society. In order to be the most perfect human being on earth, one must first be educated. Abu Lays Samarkandi in his book "Bostanul-Arifin" describes the meaning of upbringing and education: That's enough. " This idea has a special place in the works of Ibn Sina. "Whatever pandu advice you give, do it first," he said. Eastern thinkers, pedagogical scientists have justified the importance of education, its essence and content for the development of a harmoniously developed person. The process of education is a process of purposeful cooperation between educators and students.

As the President said, "The family is the stronghold of spirituality that ensures the continuity of generations." [6] Today, our main task, but also our human duty, is to bring up a harmoniously developed generation. That is why all good deeds in our country are carried out, first of all, to strengthen families and ensure a bright future for the younger generation. After all, as long as the family is healthy, the society is strong, as long as the society is strong, the country is stable. Not only the family, educational institutions but also the neighborhood are responsible for the upbringing of children. Because the upbringing of children depends on many factors, first of all, the moral and spiritual environment. Family cooperation with educational institutions is important in this regard. It is the sacred duty of each of us to form a love for the motherland, to ensure that they grow up as an enlightened and spiritual person, to create an economic and social environment for children to be spiritually mature and physically healthy.

At this point, Man is actually born for happiness and goodness, and lives with that dream. The family plays a key role in the formation of a person, in finding his place in life, in gaining respect in the country, in embodying high moral standards. Ethnic culture, traditions, moral and national values are preserved and developed. The foundation of economic and spiritual life, which determines the development of society, is laid and strengthened. It is a school of life that nurtures all the human relationships and responsibilities that must be formed in a child. The Uzbek people are by nature a childish nation. Tolerance, kindness, selflessness towards the child. These are the characteristics of our people. The role of the family in society, the importance of raising children in the family is great. Human life goes through different stages. The most important of these is the period of adolescence. This is a very delicate period, when a person is energized and goes through various paths of life. parents, teachers, educational institutions should be able to find their rightful place at the crossroads of life, to grow spiritually, to help determine their attitude to the people around them. Indeed, in the FUTURE, the possession of such qualities as morality, enlightenment, honesty, and truthfulness begins with the family and the institutions of knowledge of this small society[2].

Also, because children are the future of the nation, serious attention should be paid to their upbringing. Islam is a perfect religion that shows the first worldly happiness of man and explains the basics of this path. The hadiths of the Messenger of Allaah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) have been narrated. When children are neglected and neglected in the family and in educational institutions, it has negative consequences for their upbringing. In this regard, parents They will have to pay close attention to who they are friends with, how they spend their free time, what they spend their time on, and how they take their lessons. . Another factor influencing the upbringing of children is the misuse of the Internet, mobile phones and various social networks. It should not be forgotten that the effective use of these tools, while achieving tremendous success, also causes moral and material damage when misused. It is very important to distinguish between right and wrong information in the various streams of information provided to the Internet today, and to use it correctly and purposefully. It is necessary to raise the culture of sustainable and targeted use.

This means that the upbringing of a HUMAN BEING, which began in childhood, will eventually result in GOOD, well-mannered children who will grow up to be well-mannered and well-mannered people. Children who are brought up in a bad or bad way will grow up to be ungrateful, immoral and immoral[4]. And society and the next generation will suffer greatly from such

things. the information left behind by our forefathers on behavior requires adherence to the much-needed moral code and rules of Islamic etiquette today.

According to the results of the survey, the role of the family in the upbringing of children is very high. it does not fail to exert its influence on him. The family is the most important social institution in sociology, which plays a key role in the process of socialization of the individual. We live in the age of technology. This binds the child to a virtual life, which in turn leads to various negative consequences.

Sometimes when you look at the faces of some children, there is sadness in their eyes. It seems that there is an awkward situation in their psyche. They quickly get upset with their friends. There is a feeling of hatred in their hearts for the people around them. In their eyes, the people around them seem to be bad and incapable of doing good. Such children pay attention to everything. but also in a variety of other situations.

In short, the family and society have an equal contribution to the upbringing of children. Because when a child is educated for the first time in the family, he or she is further shaped and strengthened in pre-school education, and acquires elements of upbringing through brief explanations, advice or games. And of course, he uses his upbringing in society and in relationships. This is the basis of children's upbringing. , we need to be a good cadre and contribute to society.

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